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DFIG Based Wind Turbine System

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ABSTRACT

The significant growth of the wind power in modern electric power system increased the demand of sophisticated control algorithms which are capable to achieve high performance for the generator under variable operating conditions. Double-fed induction generator, as one type of wind power generation system, needs effective control of its power electronic interfaces to ensure stable operating characteristics, efficient power generation and satisfactory power quality. This paper designs a proposed current controller for rotor-side converter (RSC) of DFIG-based wind energy conversion system, particularly discussing the parameter tuning and performance evaluation of proportional-integral (PI) controller for stability and accuracy.

The dynamic model for the wind turbine generation system has been developed and studied under both normal and abnormal conditions by using MATLAB/Simulink. Vector-oriented control strategy is adopted in the system control framework where real power and reactive power injected to the grid are individually controlled. In this case, the rotor-side converter provides electromagnetic torque and control the amount of reactive power, and grid-side converter is applied to ensure stability of DC-link voltage and reliable transmission of power.

An indirectly power-based control structure is applied for rotor circuit, which helps generator to adapt to rapid changes in reactive power and increase its transient dynamics. With the proposed PI-based current control scheme, fluctuations in rotor currents are diminished and undesired fluctuations in power generation are suppressed.

In addition, resonance in control scheme is introduced so that to increase the tracking ability of AC reference currents and minimize the steady state error for the specific frequencies. Simulation is carried out on a 1.5 MW DFIG wind power system and the result demonstrate the practicability, robustness and advanced control performance of the proposed approach for the application.

Keywords:- *Doubly-Fed Induction Generator (DFIG), Grid Side Converter (GSC), Proportional-Integral (PI) controller, Rotor Side Converter (RSC), and Wind Turbine (WT)*

INTRODUCTION

Throughout the globe, electrical power systems are evolving toward the development of clean and reliable electric energy sources. Electricity consumption has risen significantly and combined with increased environmental awareness; conventional power plants relying on fossil fuel and their consequent CO₂ emissions will need to diminish. Consequently, renewable energy forms are rapidly entering the mainstream electrical networks at an increasing rate and wind power has established itself as an effective and scalable source of both utility-scale and distributed power generation in recent years. Wind power systems do not involve any fuel combustion, making them clean in terms of operations and suitable for planning long-term energy production.

Despite these significant advantages over the conventional forms of generation, wind energy is affected by the volatile characteristics of the wind which can be addressed using appropriate engineering design. The wind speed at any particular instant varies significantly based on a myriad of meteorological effects, terrain and geographic variations and seasonal patterns.

As such the rate of change of turbine rotational speed and mechanical torque can also vary greatly resulting in corresponding variations in the output electrical power supplied to the grid. Fluctuations in electrical power supplied to the grid may cause voltage magnitude and system frequency variations particularly in systems containing a large number of interconnected wind generators. It is imperative to ensure that these systems remain stable under all fluctuating operating conditions.

Variable speed operation using the doubly-fed induction generator (DFIG) has become commonplace for operation in modern wind power systems, where adjustable rotational speed improves performance and reduces mechanical stress on moving components. The DFIG has mechanical flexibility and enhanced electrical control capabilities.

In this arrangement the generator stator is connected to the electrical grid, whereas the rotor is coupled through a pair of bidirectional power electronic converters to control the power flow between the rotor circuitry and the grid.

The performance of the DFIG system relies critically on the control performance of the respective power electronic converters. There are two separate converter circuits employed: the rotor-side converter (RSC) and the grid-side converter (GSC). RSC controls the torque of the generator and manages the exchange of reactive power between the generator and the grid, while the GSC controls the DC-link voltage and the transfer of power between the rotor circuit and the grid.

Operating performance requirements for generating units are increasingly stringent, requiring operation within strict voltage and frequency limits, fault tolerance and smooth power transfer. As national grids become "smarter" and the influence of distributed power sources grows the complexity of operation continues to escalate and maintaining controllable power and current flow to ensure system stability is critical. Improved current control will enhance energy conversion efficiency and reduce mechanical and electrical stress on components ultimately reducing maintenance requirements.

Conventional controllers such as the proportional-integral controller (PI controller) have been successfully employed in industrial applications for many years due to their robustness and ease of implementation. PI controllers provide accurate steady state control however if the system response is faster than what the PI controller can cope with the performance can significantly degrade. In wind power systems a lack of controller performance in the presence of significant dynamics and disturbances can result in slower response rates, overshoots and undesirable oscillations.

In light of these considerations, the primary focus of this research is to

achieve improved performance of the current controller for the RSC part of the grid connected DFIG. A proportional-integral controller for improved current control has been developed and optimized. The behaviour of the system has been simulated in MATLAB/Simulink under various conditions to evaluate the response characteristics and efficacy of the controller.

With the massive increase in electricity production from wind power generation, considerable effort has been invested in the study of improving the control performance and steady-state operation of grid-connected wind turbine generators. Among different types of generator technology employed in a modern wind power system, doubly fed induction generator (DFIG) is currently the predominant choice for its capacity of wide speed operation and flexible electrical power control to the grid. To facilitate increasing penetration of renewables, stable grid interaction between the wind turbines and the utility grid has become an important technical requirement. Thus, research focused on design of advanced converter controllers to increase system stability, reduce oscillations and fulfill grid code requirements has been actively conducted.

Early research work has addressed the dynamic performance of the wind turbine generators under disturbances. Large transient currents and electromagnetic stresses are observed during voltage dip or grid fault conditions, which can endanger the integrity of power electronic devices if the controllers are not well-designed [1]. In addition, voltage imbalance on the grid has been found to produce torque pulsations and dc-link voltage ripples, hence degrading the efficiency and power

quality [3]. Various coordinated converter control methods have been proposed in order to achieve grid voltage stability under low-voltage riding conditions and others [9], [15]. Also analytical controller designs that guarantee robust performance under voltage distortion have been introduced [14]. Advanced fault-tolerant control scheme is able to keep operating during asymmetrical faults while injecting reactive power support to enhance grid stability [19], [20].

Another relevant area is development of models for wind energy conversion systems. Integrated simulation tools were designed to simulate aerodynamic, mechanical and electrical dynamics interaction within wind turbines. The developed models enable engineers to examine system dynamic performance before actual field tests. The simulation frameworks combining the effects of wind turbulence generation, the dynamics of the wind turbine and the electrical machine control have been widely used to reveal the impacts of wind variability on wind turbine performances [2].

Simplified turbine models focusing on torque and power characteristic has also been introduced to aid design-oriented simulation studies [13]. Detailed analyses on operation of variable-speed wind turbines under changing wind speed based on computational evaluation on system stability and efficiency were reported in [18]. Controller designs to extract the maximal power from the wind energy systems, and the dynamic characteristics of these systems were also analysed through simulation tool like MATLAB/Simulink [25]. Correlation between the wind speed and output power was investigated [27]. In addition, focus has been put on designing efficient current regulation strategy of DFIG

system. The commonly used proportional-integral (PI) current controllers is simple and robust in application.

However, the current controller structures capable of quick transient response and efficient disturbance rejection are urgently required. Hybrid PI/resonant controllers have been developed to effectively reject harmonics and improve the accuracy of current tracking under unbalanced system conditions [4]. Moreover, simple controller structures that realize sequence component control without using complicated signal decomposition were proposed in [5] to reduce the computation requirement. Analytical controller design methods are proposed based on pole placement to guarantee desired damping ratio and bandwidth [6]. A number of experiments demonstrated the capability of a robust current controller in tracking the stator current and regulating machine operation under parameter variations, load disturbances and rotor speed changes [11]. Tunings of PI/resonant controller to decrease setting time and overshoot were performed [17].

Comparative studies based on predictive and adaptive control are conducted on current regulation control strategies for their harmonics and transient suppression characteristics [26]. The performance of resonant current control was tested under sinusoidal reference signal input, showing that the steady-state error can be completely eliminated [31].

Vector control and power regulation studies for wind turbines have also yielded remarkable results. Integrated control strategies for regulating active and reactive power and providing voltage support for grid-connected wind turbines were reported [7]. Performance comparisons among direct and indirect

control methods showed that simplified controllers provide comparable steady-state characteristics with modest implementation efforts [8]. The performance of PI controllers in vector control was examined for stability analysis under variation of wind speed [10]. Experiments on laboratory prototypes verify that direct power control can be capable of tracing power reference precisely in different working states [12]. The work on the improved control structure which satisfy grid codes while maintaining power quality was demonstrated in [24]. Transient performance of indirect control has shown better response than direct control strategy in general [30]. In addition, hysteresis-based power regulation was performed to control output power by injecting desired rotor current [33].

Recent research efforts explore novel control strategies for dealing with nonlinear operation in modern systems. Nonlinear field-oriented control approaches have been designed to cope with improved dynamic performance and stability under nonlinear control circumstances [21]. Fuzzy logic controllers were designed and they showed more promising outcomes than PI controller regarding regulation accuracy of generator current under variable wind speed conditions [22], [28].

Based on artificial intelligence approaches, such as neural network or adaptive fuzzy controller, more efficient controllers were developed to mitigate nonlinear and disturbance problems better than conventional PI control [32]. In addition, virtual inertia control strategies have been proposed to achieve better frequency regulation in modern interconnected power systems with converter-based generation units [34].

Despite these remarkable progresses in wind turbine control technologies, a number of technical problems remain in practical application.

The fluctuating wind speed generates oscillations in the rotor current, electromagnetic torque and output power, which degrades the quality and efficiency. Coordinating rotor and grid side converters under transient operating states is complicated. Moreover, performance of PI current controller is highly dependent on parameter tuning, poor parameter tuning leads to slow response, overshoot or instability during transient period.

Hence the main problem of this research work is to develop an advanced current control strategy for the rotor side converter of DFIG in grid-connected wind turbine generator to improve accuracy of current control, oscillations damping and dynamic stability performance via proper design and simulation of the controller under realistic operation condition.

DESIGN, MATHEMATICAL MODELLING AND CONTROL

Standard Doubly-Fed Induction Generator (DFIG) consists of a wound rotor induction machine where stator is directly connected to the three-phase utility grid while the rotor circuit is connected to it through a back-to-back bidirectional PWM converter as shown in Fig. 1. This structure provides full range variable speed operation over both sub-synchronous and super-synchronous region, and at a partial converter rating. A DFIG can export/import the slip power on the rotor side depending on its operating speed and can send the generated power to the grid continuously when running at steady state on the stator side.

The Rotor Side Converter Control as shown in Fig. 2 utilizes indirect vector control method to independently control the active and reactive power of stator by separated control in synchronous d-q reference frame. Based on the desired reference power values, the reference components for rotor current is calculated, in which the quadrature-axis current determines the active power (electromagnetic torque) and the direct-

axis current controls reactive power, by means of cascaded PI controllers and PWM based voltage synthesis. The Grid Side Converter Control shown in Fig. 3 regulates the stability of DC-link voltage, ensures balanced power delivery by regulating filter current, and obtains zero reactive power reference to realize approximately unity power factor at the grid side.

Fig.3:-DFIG Grid Side Converter Control.

Fig.4:-Wind Turbine Power Characteristic at Wind Speed of 12 m/sec.

For a wind speed of 12 m/s the power output of the turbine increases with rotor speed up to a certain optimum point, which is also the point where the maximum aerodynamic efficiency occurs. As the speed continues to increase beyond this point less power is extracted, as the tip speed ratio is higher than optimum.

SIMULATION AND RESULTS

The performance of the DFIG system during dynamics using indirect vector control with outer power loop and PI regulators has been assessed. Several electromechanical and electrical variables, such as the rotor angular speed, the electromagnetic torque, the stator active and reactive power, the d and q components of rotor current in the synchronous reference frame, the terminal voltage and current, and the D.C-link voltage stability, are analysed. During the considered simulation time the wind speed is kept constant (12m/s) and,

as a consequence, the dynamic responses are solely dependent on the response of the controllers, not the aerodynamic variables.

The dynamics of the control system is also tested by changing the values of stator active and reactive powers in steps. It is verified that the controller tracks the changes made by the user with high accuracy and without large overshoot. The setting time is roughly 1s, meaning that control of the D.C-link voltage, and of both stator power, are regulated correctly by cascading PI control loops. The DC-link voltage does not deviate significantly from 1200V which is evidence that the RSC and the GSC are operating in cooperation. The above simulations clearly show that the indirectly control scheme with PI regulation leads to effective, decoupled power control and stable rotational speed with proper electrical characteristics during the normal operation.

Fig.5:-Dynamic Response of Rotor Angular Velocity under Indirect PI-Based Control

The rotor speed can be observed to undergo a small transient decrease in the beginning and eventually stabilize, confirming the good speed regulation of the indirect PI-based control scheme.

Good damping and consistent synchronization of the generator under nominal load are confirmed from the settling response.

Fig.6:-Regulation of DC-Link Voltage Using Coordinated Converter Control

Fig.7:- Transient Behaviour of Active Power During Reference Tracking

Fig.8:-Reactive Power Compensation Performance of the Controlled DFIG System

The dc-link voltage is kept close to the reference with short transient variation, shows good coordination of the rotor side

and grid side converter. This also presents the energy flow balance and robust voltage control under varying operation.

Fig.9:- Voltage Profile of the DFIG under Indirect Vector Control

The active and reactive power shows quick transient response after the step command for reference, smoothly converging to the desired value and small steady state error. From these properties, the ability of decoupled power regulation and the fast dynamic tracking of indirect PI control are illustrated.

The three phase voltages are balanced sinusoidal, which have constant

amplitude and frequency. It means the synchronization to the grid is correct and the control of the converter operates stable.

The currents have symmetric sinusoidal waveform, and the amplitudes are same with each other. It can conclude the current regulation is working well and the power transfer is reliable using the adopted control strategy (indirect PI).

Fig.10:- Stator Current Waveform Demonstrating Stable Converter Operation

CONCLUSION

In this paper, the detailed modelling and dynamic simulation of the grid connected wind energy conversion system using a Doubly Fed Induction Generator (DFIG) have been developed with the help of MATLAB/Simulink. An analytical wind turbine model and the coupled controlling of the RSC and GSC for independently controlled active and reactive powers have been studied. The indirect control with suitable tuned PI controllers used in the system can make the generator operate stable throughout the entire operating conditions, and the dc-link voltage and grid power flow steadily.

The simulation results have shown that the system can be well controlled to obtain smooth dynamic performance with reduced transient deviation and quick steady state settling time, and also achieve the decoupling between active and reactive powers. In addition, the rotor speed was stable and the electrical parameters of the DFIG are properly damped so that the selected control structure is proper for a wind energy conversion system and it makes the voltage well-controlled and the power transferred to the grid smooth.

In conclusion, the control approach based on PI controllers proposed in this paper is effective, efficient, and simple in the control of DFIG-based wind energy generation systems under steady wind speeds. The results will provide a good technical basis for integration of stable renewable energy system into present power network.

REFERENCES

1. Dawei Xiang, Li Ran, Peter J. Tavner, and Shunchang Yang, "Control of a Doubly Fed Induction Generator in a Wind Turbine during Grid Fault Ride Through", IEEE Transactions On Energy Conversion, Vol. 21, No. 3, September 2006.
2. Roohollah Fadaeinedjad, Mehrdad Moallem, and Gerry Moschopoulos, "Simulation of a Wind Turbine with Doubly Fed Induction Generator by FAST and Simulink", IEEE Transactions on Energy Conversion, Vol. 23, No. 2, June 2008.
3. Lingling Fan, Haiping Yin, Zhixin Miao, "A Novel Control Scheme for DFIG-based Wind Energy Systems under Unbalanced Grid Conditions", Electric Power Systems Research, April 30, 2010.
4. Van-Tung Phan, Hong-Hee Leey, and Tae-Won Chun, "An Improved Control Strategy Using a PI-Resonant Controller for an Unbalanced Stand-alone Doubly-Fed Induction Generator", Journal of Power Electronics, Vol. 10, No. 2, March 2010.
5. Van-Tung Phan and Hong-Hee Lee, "Enhanced Proportional-Resonant Current Controller for Unbalanced Stand-alone DFIG based Wind Turbines", Journal of Electrical Engineering and Technology Vol. 5, No. 3, pp. 443-450, 2010.
7. Changjin Liu, Wenjie Chen, Frede Blaabjerg, Dehong Xu, "Optimized Design of Resonant Controller for Stator Current Harmonic Compensation in DFIG Wind Turbine Systems", 2012 Twenty-Seventh Annual IEEE Applied Power Electronics Conference and Exposition (APEC), Orlando, FL, 2012, pp. 2038-2044.
8. Shuhui Li, Senior Member, Timothy A. Haskew, Keith A. Williams, and Richard P. Swatloski, "Control of DFIG Wind Turbine with Direct-Current Vector Control Configuration", IEEE Transactions On Sustainable Energy, Vol. 3, No. 1, January 2012.

9. A. Dekhane, S. Lekhchine, T. Bahi, S. Ghodelbourg, H. Merabet, "DFIG Modeling and Control in a Wind Energy Conversion System", 2012 First International Conference on Renewable Energies and Vehicular Technology, Hammamet, 2012, pp. 287-292.
10. Yan, Meng Wang, Zhan-Feng Song and Chang-Liang Xia, "Proportional-Resonant Control of Doubly-Fed Induction Generator Wind Turbines for Low Voltage Ride Through Enhancement", *Energies* 2012, 5, 4758-4778.
11. A. Medjber, A. Moualdia, A. Mellit et M. A. Guessoum, "Comparative Study between Direct and Indirect Vector Control Applied to a wind Turbine Equipped with a Double-fed Asynchronous Machine Article", *International Journal of Renewable Energy Research* Medjber Ahmed et al., Vol.3, No.1, 2013.
12. Edin Golubovic, E.Emre Ozsoyy, Metin Gokasan, Asif Sabanovic, "Design and Analysis of Robust Rotor Current Controller for Doubly Fed Induction Generator", *IECON 2013 - 39th Annual Conference of the IEEE Industrial Electronics Society*, Vienna, 2013, pp. 5260-5265.
13. Sevki Demirbas, Sertac Bayhan, "Active and Reactive Power Control of Doubly Fed Induction Generator using Direct Power Control Technique", 4th International Conference on Power Engineering, Energy and Electrical Drives, Istanbul, Turkey, 13-17 May 2013.
14. Phlearn Jansuya and Yuttana Kumsuwan, "Design of MATLAB/Simulink Modeling of Fixed-Pitch Angle Wind Turbine Simulator", *10th Eco-Energy and Materials Science and Engineering, Energy Proceedings* 34 (2013), 362 – 370.
15. Heng Nian, Yipeng Song, "Optimised Parameter Design of Proportional Integral and Resonant Current Regulator for Doubly Fed Induction Generator during Grid Voltage Distortion", *IET Renewable Power Generation*, 2014, Vol. 8, Issue 3, pp. 299–313.
16. Heng Nian, and Yipeng Song, "Direct Power Control of Doubly Fed Induction Generator under Distorted Grid Voltage", *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, Vol. 29, No. 2, February 2014.
17. Amevi Acakpovi, Essel Ben Hagan, "A Wind Turbine System Model using a Doubly -Fed Induction Generator (DFIG)", *International Journal of Computer Applications* (0975 – 8887) Volume 90 – No. 15, March 2014.
18. Fernando Ortiz Martinz, Kelly Caroline Mingorancia de Carvalho, Naji Rajai Nasri Ama, Wilson Komatsu, Lourenyo Matakas Junior, "Optimized Tuning Method of Stationary Frame Proportional Resonant Current Controllers", *2014 International Power Electronics Conference (IPEC-Hiroshima 2014 - ECCE ASIA)*, Hiroshima, 2014, pp. 2988-2995.
19. F. Senani, A. Rahab and H. Benalla, "Modeling and Control of Active and Reactive Powers of Wind Energy Conversion System in Variable Speed Based on DFIG", *Revue des Energies Renouvelables* Vol. 18 No. 4 (2015), 643 – 655.
20. Debirupa Hore, Runumi Sarma, "Modeling, Analysis and Operation of Wind Driven DFIG Under Unbalance Network Voltage Conditions: A Review", *International Journal Current Research Rev*, Vol. 7, Issue 1, January 2015.
21. D. V. N. Ananth, L. B. S. Vinod, "Performance of DFIG Based Grid

- Connected System Under Different Grid Faults Using PI and PIR Controller in RSC”, International Journal of Science, Engineering and Technology Research (IJSETR), Volume 4, Issue 9, September 2015.
22. Hala Alami Aroussi, Elmostafa Ziani, Badre Bossoufi, “Speed Control of the Doubly Fed Induction Generator Applied to A Wind System”, Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology, 31st January 2016. Vol. 83. No.3.
 23. Marouane El Azzaoui and Hassane Mahmoudi, “Fuzzy Control of A Doubly Fed Induction Generator Based Wind Power System”, WSEAS Transactions on Power Systems, E-ISSN: 2224-350X, Volume 12, 2017.
 24. Santiago Arnaltes, Jose Luis Rodriguez-Amenedo and Miguel E. Montilla-DJesus, “Control of Variable Speed Wind Turbines with Doubly Fed Asynchronous Generators for Stand-alone Applications”, Energies 2018, 11, 26.
 25. F. Mazouz, S. Belkacem, Y. Harbouche, R. Abdessemed and S. Ouchen, “Active and Reactive Power Control of a DFIG for Variable Speed Wind Energy Conversion”, Proceedings of the 6th International Conference on Systems and Control, University of Batna 2, Batna, Algeria, May 7-9, 2017.
 26. Manale Bouderbala, Ahmed Lagrioui, Mohmmmed Taoussi, Madiha El Ghamrasni, “Modeling and Power Controls of Wind Energy Conversion Systems Based on Doubly Fed Induction Generator”, 2018 6th International Renewable and Sustainable Energy Conference (IRSEC), Rabat, Morocco, 2018, pp. 1-6.
 27. Ujjwol Tamrakar, Dipesh Shrestha, Naresh Malla, Zhen Ni, Timothy M. Hansen, Indraman Tamrakar and Reinaldo Tonkoski, “Comparative Analysis of Current Control Techniques to Support Virtual Inertia Applications”, Applied Science 2018, 8, 2695.
 28. Mohammed A. Ibrahim, Dr. Fawaz S. Abdullah, Bashar M. Salih, “Modeling and Simulation of 1.5MW Wind Turbine”, International Journal of Applied Engineering Research ISSN 0973-4562 Vol. 13, No. 10 (2018), pp. 7882-7888.
 29. Othmane Zamzoum, Youness El Mourabit, Mustapha Errouha, Aziz Derouich, Abdelaziz El Ghzizal, “Power Control of Variable Speed Wind Turbine Based on Doubly Fed Induction Generator Using Indirect Field-Oriented Control With Fuzzy Logic Controllers For Performance Optimization”, Energy Science Engineering, 2018; 6:408–423.
 30. A. Bala Narayana, P. Govind Raju, K. V. Ramana, “Proportional Resonant Controller with Resonant Harmonic Compensators for Three-Phase Multilevel Inverter”, International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET), e-ISSN: 2395-0056 Vol. 05 Issue 06, June-2018.
 31. Mbarek Taleb and Mohamed Cherkaoui, “Active and Reactive Power Control of Doubly Fed Induction Generator Wind Turbines to Answer Grid Codes Requirements”, Journal of Clean Energy Technologies, Vol. 6, No. 2, March 2018.
 32. Preetha Sreekumar, Ravichandran Danthakani, Suhas P. Veettil, “Implementation of Proportional-Resonant Controller in an Autonomous Distributed Generation Unit”, 2018 Advances in Science and Engineering Technology International Conferences (ASET), Abu Dhabi, 2018, pp. 1-5.

33. Sabah Louarem, Djamel Eddine Chouaib Belkhiat, Tarek Bouktir, Saad Belkhiat, "An Efficient Active and Reactive Power Control of DFIG for a Wind Power Generator", Engineering, Technology and Applied Science Research Vol. 9, No. 5, 2019, 4775-4782.
34. Danduboyina Dimple, Dr. Yerra Sreenivasa Rao, "Direct Power Control of Grid Connected Double-Fed Induction Generator in Wind Energy Conversion System", International Journal for Modern Trends in Science and Technology ISSN: 2455-3778 Vol. 05, Issue No. 08, August 2019.
35. Kumaravel S., Vinu Thomas, Terence O'Donnell and Ashok S., "Virtual Synchronous Machine Control of Grid Connected Power Electronic Converters for Power System Applications", Journal of Engineering Research Vol. 7, No. (2), June 2019, pp. 196-209.